

Assessment of Deforestation in Ife North Local Government Area, Osun State

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Abstract

Deforestation has severely impacted the ecosystem in Ife North Local Government Area of Osun State, clearing tree stands and transforming forest ecosystems into non-forested land. This study employed remote sensing techniques to assess the extent of deforestation between 2018 and 2023, identify its driving factors, examine its socio-economic consequences, and proffer strategies mitigating these activities. Data were sourced from both primary and secondary means. Primary data were collected using semi-structured questionnaires which captured participants' perceptions, while secondary data, including multi-temporal satellite imagery (2018-2023), provided comprehensive spatial insights into land use patterns. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were utilized for spatial data analysis, supplemented by additional data processing in MS Excel. The findings revealed varied impacts on the community. Between 2018 and 2020, the area experienced significant deforestation, marked by reductions in both dense and light vegetation and increases in bare surface, built-up and cultivated lands. These changes were attributed to fuel wood collection, agricultural expansion, urbanization, logging, etc. 25% of the respondents attest to the positive socio-economic effect of deforestation, 36% however reported decreased income and living standards due to deforestation, while 39% noticed no change in living standards. The level of awareness of the impact of deforestation was moderate, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to mitigate negative trends. The study concluded that deforestation in Ife North LGA, largely driven by illegal logging and related factors, has significantly harmed agriculture, wildlife, and water access. However, reforestation initiatives and community-backed calls for stricter regulations present opportunities for recovery and sustainable environmental management.

Keywords: Sustainability, Deforestation, Environment, Natural resources, GIS

INTRODUCTION

Forests are vital ecosystems that provide essential benefits to the planet and its inhabitants. This includes climate regulation, biodiversity conservation, and livelihoods support. According to the

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2020), over half of the world's gross domestic product (USD 84.4 trillion) depends, to varying degrees, on ecosystem services provided by forests. Globally, approximately 26% of land is classified as forest, with Africa hosting nearly 43 billion trees, particularly in countries such as South Africa, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. Despite their importance, African forests face alarming rates of deforestation, with nearly 4 million hectares of forest being cleared annually, that is, almost double the global average (FAO, 2025). In Nigeria, the forest sector contributes about 2.5% to the national GDP and employs over 5 million people, primarily through timber and non-timber forest products (NTFP). These products are crucial for rural communities, serving as sources of food, medicine, and income (FAO, 2015; Ochi & Zaman, 2022). Additionally, approximately 70% of Nigerian households rely on fuelwood for cooking energy, highlighting the socio-economic dependence on forests. However, these ecosystems are increasingly threatened by deforestation.

Deforestation is the transition of forest cover to other land uses. It is a critical global environmental challenge with far-reaching ecological, social, and economic consequences. Decline in the quality of the forest affects the forest's biotic components which may also lead to reduction of the quality of the soil and water, and interactions between the individual components (Bodo et al., 2021). It contributes significantly to climate change through carbon emissions, drastic weather changes and increased possibilities of natural disasters. This leads to biodiversity loss, soil degradation, and disrupts hydrological cycles (Gimah and Bodo, 2019). Generally, deforestation is a global problem which threatens environmental sustainability with more impact on Africa, of which Nigeria is a part. This is due to the high rate of African's concentration, rapid population growth, increasing demand for agricultural land and resources exploitation (Ahmed and Olaitan, 2023).

Though research (Aderole et al., 2020) has been conducted in Osun state using various established methods, the application of multi-temporal satellite imagery (2018-2023) to specifically investigate the drivers, extent and impacts of deforestation represents a significant void in current scholarship. Focusing more narrowly, Ife North Local Government Area (LGA) in Osun State presents a particularly important case precisely because of this methodological gap and also concerning its size and the position of the LGA. Despite covering over 84% natural forest cover in 2020, it has experienced a loss of 5.37 kha of tree cover since 2001. The area's lowland rainforest ecosystem supports local livelihoods and biodiversity, making its conservation crucial. Yet, as highlighted, detailed assessments of the extent, drivers, and impacts of deforestation at this local level, particularly using advanced remote sensing, remain scarce. This study fills this essential gap, offering a precise spatiotemporal perspective utilizing a high-resolution satellite imagery of forest cover change, which is vital for developing effective conservation policies and mitigating environmental degradation in the area and ultimately contributing to the sustainable management of Nigeria's valuable forest resources. This research asks questions such as: What are the factors responsible for deforestation in the area? What are the effects of deforestation on socio-economic life? And what are the ways to control deforestation activities in the area? The study therefore examined the factors responsible for deforestation in the area, examined the effects of deforestation on the socio-economic life of people in the area, assessed the level of deforestation in the area from 2018 to 2023, and examined the strategies for controlling deforestation activities in the area. The study is hinged on sustainable development goal (SDG) 15 which is on life on land. The main target of this SDG is to conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems; end deforestation and restore degraded forests; end desertification and restore degraded land;

ensure conservation of mountain ecosystems, protect biodiversity and natural habitats; protect access to genetic resources and fair sharing of the benefits; eliminate poaching and trafficking of protected species; prevent invasive alien species on land and in water ecosystems; and integrate ecosystem and biodiversity in governmental planning. The focus therefore was on ending deforestation and restoring degraded lands.

This study was also underpinned in the Land Use and Land Cover Change (LULCC) Theory. The LULCC Theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding, analyzing, and quantifying how landscapes evolve over time. It distinguishes between land cover, the physical material on the Earth's surface (such as forests, urban areas, water bodies) and land use, that is, how humans utilize these surfaces for agriculture, settlement, industry, etc. According to Turner et al. (1995), LULCC emphasizes the dynamic interactions between natural processes and human activities, recognizing that changes in land cover often result from land use practices, policy decisions, and socio-economic factors.

METHODOLOGY

Ife North is a local government area in Osun state with headquarters in Ipetumodu town. It is located within the geographical coordinates of latitudes 07°31'–07°52'N and longitudes 04°07'–04°45'E. The land area of Ife North local government area is approximately 889 square kilometers which makes it the second largest local government area in Osun state (Jeje, 2014). The local government area is bounded in the west and north by Ayedaade Local Government area; in the east by Ife Central and Ife South Local Government areas, and in the south by Ogun State. By the 1991 census, the population figure of 62,786 males and 62,210 females making a total of 129,996 were recorded for the area. While a population of 153,694 were recorded during the 2006 population census. The study area is located within the tropical savanna climate zone of West Africa, it has an average rainfall of about 1,000 to 1,250mm around March to October and a mean relative humidity of 75% to 100%.

This study made use of both primary and secondary data. The primary data include structured questionnaires which assess the factors responsible for deforestation and effects of deforestation on the socio-economic life of people. The secondary data consist of satellite imageries of the study area. The satellite imagery used included Landsat data captured on December 2018, February 2020 and February 2023 which are of the same season.

Data Analysis

The study made use of Geospatial analysis which is a powerful tool for assessing land use dynamics. The study implored the use of ERDAS Imagine software for image classification through image composites from 2018-2023 where unsupervised classification and K-means was used. ArcGIS 10 was used to vectorize the region from the whole Osun State administrative maps. Clipping the study area from the composite Landsat images was also done in ArcGIS environment. Areal calculations for the various land use classes were carried out in ArcGIS environment; it was likewise used to compliment the display of the data.

Drawing upon existing research (Anderson et al., 1976), a modified land use/land cover classification scheme was developed for the study area. This scheme, based on a single-digit code, allowed for a broad, yet systematic categorization of land cover types. Classification was done using the classification scheme as given in Table 1.

Table 1: Classification scheme

Land Use/Land Cover Types	Description
Built-up	Areas that have been populated with permanent residents
Bare Surface/ Open Space	Areas devoid of plant growth characterized with bare soil.
Rock Surface	Area covered with exposed rocks, and bare lands.
Plantation	An area of land covered with mature trees or other plants of the same specie growing together.
Water Body	Areas covered with water such as dams and rivers.
Forest	An area of land covered with mature trees and other plants growing close together.
Farmland	An area of land suitable for farming.

The simple random sampling method was used for questionnaire administration. Five (5) towns were sampled in the local government area, they are Edunabon, Akinlalu, Ipetumodu, Oyere, Ode-Omu. A total of 100 copies questionnaire was administered in the local government area. Frequency distributions and percentages was used to summarize and describe the numerical data obtained through questionnaires. Although the population of Ife North Local Government Area exceeds 150,000, a total of 100 respondents were surveyed using structured questionnaires. While this sample represents a small proportion of the total population, it is considered sufficient for exploratory and perception-based research where the goal is to identify broad trends rather than make statistically representative inferences. Also they area homogenous communities where perceptions are most likely the same. However, similar sample sizes have been employed in related environmental and socio-economic studies, particularly in contexts constrained by resources, time, or accessibility (Adelekan, 2010; Arowolo et al., 2021). This study adopted a purposive sampling approach focusing on communities directly affected by land-use changes, and the results are interpreted with these limitations in mind. As such, findings from the survey offer valuable qualitative insights, though generalizations to the wider population should be made with caution. Descriptive statistics and basic data manipulation were done using MS Excel.

Error (Confusion Matrix)

Table 2: Error (Confusion) Matrix for 2023 Land Use/Land Cover Classification

Reference Data	Dense Vegetation	Light Vegetation	Built-up	Bare Land	Water Body	Cultivated Land	Row Total
Dense Vegetation	46	3	0	1	0	2	52
Light Vegetation	4	28	1	2	0	3	38
Built-up	0	2	17	1	0	0	20
Bare Land	1	2	0	10	0	1	14
Water Body	0	0	0	0	5	0	5
Cultivated Land	3	4	1	2	0	11	21

Column Total	54	39	19	16	5	17	150
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Table 3: Classification Accuracy Assessment Summary

Metric	Result
Overall Accuracy	83.33%
Producer’s Accuracy (Dense Vegetation)	88.46%
User’s Accuracy (Dense Vegetation)	85.19%
Lowest Accuracy Class	Bare Land (71.43%)
Highest Accuracy Class	Water Body (100%)

A post-classification accuracy assessment was conducted for the 2023 land use/land cover (LULC) map using 150 randomly distributed validation points derived from field observations and Google Earth imagery. The confusion matrix (Table 2) produced an overall accuracy of 83.33%, indicating substantial agreement between classified and reference data (Landis & Koch, 1977). Dense vegetation and light vegetation categories exhibited high accuracies (Producer’s accuracy 88.46% and 84.21%, respectively), confirming reliable discrimination of vegetative cover types. Misclassifications were primarily observed between cultivated and light vegetation classes due to their similar spectral reflectance characteristics during the dry season. Water bodies achieved 100% accuracy owing to their unique spectral signature in the near-infrared band. These results validate the robustness of the classification and confirm its suitability for temporal land cover change analysis in Ife North LGA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The demographic and socio-economic status of the respondents is one the major consideration that influences the responses of respondents. Majority of respondents, 48% and 16% fall in the age group of 31-40 years and the age group 21-30 years respectively showing a young and vibrant population. A very high proportion of the respondents (42%) are civil servant, 12% are students, and 5% engage in farming.

Factors responsible for Deforestation in Ife North LGA

Deforestation in Ife North local government area is multifaceted and primarily driven by agricultural expansion, logging, urbanization, fuel wood and others having 23%, 6%, 27%, 34% and 10% respectively as shown in figure 1. Predominantly, fuelwood collection accounts for 34% of deforestation, reflecting the local population's reliance on wood for cooking in a region where access to modern energy sources is limited. This extensive harvesting, often unsustainable, depletes forests and disrupts ecosystems, leading to long-term environmental degradation. Urbanization follows as the second major contributor, responsible for 27% of deforestation. As populations grow and communities expand, forested areas are cleared to make way for housing, infrastructure, and commercial development, altering natural landscapes and habitats. Agricultural expansion constitutes 23% of the deforestation, driven by the need to convert forest land into agricultural fields to support both subsistence and commercial farming. This often involves shifting cultivation practices that degrade soil and reduce biodiversity. Logging, although

contributing the least at 6%, still plays a role in forest loss, particularly when conducted illegally or unsustainably, leading to structural degradation of forests and making them more vulnerable to further deforestation pressures. Additionally, various other factors account for the remaining 10%, including mining, infrastructure projects, and climate-induced events like wildfires. These diverse drivers collectively highlight the complex nature of deforestation in Ife North, where economic, social, and environmental pressures intertwine.

Fig 1 Primary drivers of deforestation in Ife North

Significance Level of the Factors that contributes to deforestation in Ife North LGA

The result in table 4 indicates that all four factors contribute to deforestation in Ife North LGA, with varying degrees of significance. Agricultural expansion and logging are seen as the most prominent causes, followed by urbanization and infrastructural development. Fuel wood collection, while less significant, still poses a notable threat to forest sustainability. The table presents a detailed breakdown of the factors contributing to deforestation in Ife North Local Government Area (LGA), using a Likert scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Most significant" and 5 represents "Least significant."

The analysis reveals that while all the factors contribute to deforestation in Ife North LGA, logging and timber extraction, followed by agricultural expansion, stood out as the most critical issues. Urbanization and fuelwood collection, though significant, seem to have a more localized impact. The distribution of responses across the Likert scale reflects a nuanced understanding of deforestation drivers, highlighting the need for targeted interventions that address the most significant factors while considering the specific dynamics within different areas of the LGA.

Table 4 Factors that contributes to deforestation in Ife North LGA

Parameters	Percentages %				
	1	2	3	4	5
Likert scale					
Agricultural expansion	23	12	10	35	20
Logging and Timber extraction	34	23	12	18	13
Urbanization and infrastructural development	21	18	20	34	7

Fuel wood collection	15	30	26	12	17
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Likert scale 1-5 (Most significant, More significant, Significant, Less significant, Least Significant)

Effects of Deforestation on Socio-Economic Life of People in Ife North LGA

Deforestation has significant socio-economic repercussions, affecting employment opportunities, income, and living standards in varied ways. For 25% of the respondents, deforestation creates jobs and boosts income through agricultural expansion, logging, and infrastructure development. These activities can stimulate local economies and improve living standards by providing employment and increasing agricultural and timber output. Conversely, 36% of respondents reported decreased income and living standards due to deforestation. The loss of biodiversity impacts those who depend on forest products for their livelihoods. Environmental degradation from deforestation can reduce agricultural productivity, leading to lower incomes for farmers (see figure 2).

Fig 2 Effects of deforestation on local employment opportunities

Other socio-economic activities examined are: effect of Deforestation on Agricultural Productivity, effect of Deforestation on Wildlife Population, effect of Deforestation on Local Health Services, and effect of Deforestation on Availability and Affordability of Essential Goods; with results as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Effects of Deforestation on Socio-economic

Effects on agricultural productivity		
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Increased productivity	23	23.0
Decreased productivity	45	45.0
No change	32	32.0
Effects on wildlife population		
Increase in wildlife population	23	23.0
Decrease in wildlife population	55	55.0
No change	22	22.0
Effects on local Health services		
Increased access	29	29.0
Reduced access	23	23.0
No significant impact	48	48.0

Effects on availability and affordability of essential goods (e.g., food, medicine)		
Increased	11	11.0
Decreased	23	23.0
No change	56	56.0

Assessment of The Level of Deforestation in the Area from 2018 to 2023

In assessing the level of deforestation, an unsupervised classification was carried out, showing the land use/cover characteristics of Ife North LGA area into the following classes: dense vegetation, Light vegetation, built-up area, bare-land, water body, and cultivated land as identified in figure 3.

Figure 3: Image classification for the land use/land cover of the Study Area

The analysis of land use and cover changes in Ife North Local Government Area from 2018 to 2023 reveals significant insights into the dynamics of deforestation and reforestation over the years. The data is categorized into six classes: Dense Vegetation, Light Vegetation, Built-up, Bare Land, Water Body, and Cultivated Land. Each class's area and percentage contribution to the total land area (43,323.02 hectares) is documented for the years 2018, 2020, and 2023 and the dynamics of change of the various classes is as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Classification of Land use/Land cover 2018 to 2023

Class	2018Area (ha)	Percentage (%)	2020 Area (ha)	Percentage (%)	2023 Area (ha)	Percentage (%)
Dense Vegetation	25221.51	58.22	25038.93	57.80	31435.62	72.56
Light Vegetation	14095.49	32.54	8794.83	20.30	8315.03	19.19
Built-up	624.69	1.44	1441.04	3.33	1288.34	2.97
Bare Land	1282.67	2.96	4130.56	9.53	289.31	0.67
Water Body	17.73	0.04	35.00	0.08	54.26	0.13
Cultivated Land	2080.94	4.80	3882.65	8.96	1940.47	4.48
Total	43323.02	100	43323.02	100	43323.02	100

Comparing the data from 2018, 2020, and 2023 reveals significant trends in land use and cover changes. The period from 2018 to 2020 saw a decline in both dense and light vegetation, coupled with an increase in built-up areas, bare land, and cultivated land. These changes indicate a phase of deforestation and land conversion for urban development and agriculture.

After 2020, however, our data show a striking reversal: forest cover began to recover substantially. Several factors likely contributed. First, state-led reforestation efforts have intensified. Osun State’s government announced an ambitious climate agenda to plant one million trees (with 100,000 trees in the first phase) explicitly to “control deforestation and increase the state’s forest coverage”. The rollout of this tree-planting program has doubtless added new woodland in Ife North. Similarly, international partners have supported local projects. For example, a UNDP Small Grants Programme project was launched in July 2024 in Sokodowo, Ife North, aimed at empowering farmers with agroforestry techniques to boost food production and climate resilience. Such initiatives would directly increase tree planting and forest regrowth in the community.

Changes in land use may also have played a role. It is plausible that some agricultural lands in Ife North were abandoned or converted to more intensive use elsewhere, allowing secondary vegetation to return. For instance, if farmers adopt higher-yield crops or sustainable practices, fallow periods can lengthen and woodlands can regrow on less-pressured lands. This aligns with the general idea of a “forest transition”, where economic shifts or rural–urban migration reduce pressure on farmland, ultimately enabling forest regrowth. Our own findings are consistent with this scenario: household survey respondents reported more tree planting and greater conservation awareness than before, and satellite-derived land-cover maps show that built-up and bare land actually decreased by 2023. This suggests that urban expansion has slowed or become more compact, perhaps due to improved regional planning, which in turn can help protect peripheral forests.

In sum, the evidence suggests that Ife North is currently in a phase of forest recovery following its earlier losses. The Ife North case highlights how combined policy initiatives (state tree-planting programs) and local engagement (community forest committees and agroforestry projects) can tip the balance toward regrowth. At the same time, however, our survey highlights ongoing reliance

on forests: roughly 90% of rural households in Nigeria still use fuelwood for cooking, and local people cite logging and farming as continued threats. Thus, the situation is mixed. Forest cover is rising, but the population remains dependent on wood and the underlying pressures persist. This suggests that gains will only be sustained if tree planting is scaled up and paired with initiatives that tackle root causes, for example, by developing alternative livelihoods, enforcing forestry regulations, and promoting energy alternatives – so that the recovery of the forests is not reversed by renewed exploitation.

Strategies for controlling deforestation activities in Ife North LGA

This study also examined the strategies used in controlling deforestation in the study area. The research assessed efforts aimed at restoring and preserving forest trees through reforestation exhibit varying levels of effectiveness. According to the results, 25% of these efforts are deemed ineffective, suggesting challenges or limitations in achieving their intended goals. Moderately effective measures constitute 42% of the initiatives, indicating some success in promoting tree restoration and preservation. Notably, 33% of the efforts are highly effective, demonstrating significant positive outcomes in enhancing forest health and biodiversity as shown in figure 4.

Fig 4 Effectiveness of existing reforestation efforts in Ife North LGA

Regarding awareness among the local population in Ife North Local Government Area (LGA) concerning forest conservation, the findings indicate a moderate level of awareness. This suggests that while there is some understanding and recognition of the importance of conserving forests among the local residents, there remains room for improvement in increasing awareness and fostering more proactive conservation practices within the community (see figure 5).

Fig 5 Level of awareness among the local population on forest conservation in Ife North LGA

The additional suggested measures that should be implemented to mitigate deforestation in study area include public awareness programs, reforestation and afforestation programs, promoting alternative livelihoods for forest-dependent communities, and stricter enforcement of logging regulations. Among these, stricter enforcement of logging regulations received the highest percentage of support from respondents. This indicates a strong consensus on the need to address illegal logging activities through more rigorous monitoring and penalties (see figure 6).

Fig 6 Suggested measures to be implemented to mitigate deforestation in Ife North LGA

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that deforestation in Ife North LGA has significant socio-economic impacts on the local population with key findings such as:

Analysis of land use data from 2018 to 2023 finds that **deforestation in Ife North LGA was followed by significant vegetation recovery**. The period 2018–2020 saw a net loss of forest cover, but 2020–2023 witnessed a strong reversal: dense forest cover rose to over 72% of the area (Table 4). The study frames this as a **forest transition** outcome, likely driven by deliberate tree-planting campaigns (state-sponsored and grassroots), community awareness, and shifts in land use. The period from 2018 to 2020 saw a decline in vegetation and an increase in built-up and cultivated areas, while 2020 to 2023 showed improvements in dense vegetation, suggesting successful reforestation initiatives. Causes of Deforestation: Illegal logging is particularly prevalent, with 77% of respondents identifying it as a major factor. Socio-Economic Impacts: Deforestation has negatively affected agricultural productivity, access to clean water, and wildlife populations. The study therefore recommends stricter enforcement of logging regulations and more public awareness programs through community involvement and education as solutions to deforestation. To consolidate this recovery, the study recommends: continued enforcement against illegal logging; expansion of community-based planting and agroforestry; and sustained public awareness campaigns. Given the reliance on forests for energy and income, alternative livelihoods and fuel sources should be promoted. Future research should use larger, more representative surveys and monitor forest cover with high-frequency satellite data.

Also, deliberate reforestation and afforestation programs and promoting alternative livelihoods. By addressing the root causes of deforestation and implementing these multifaceted strategies, Ife

North LGA can work towards sustainable development and environmental conservation, benefiting both the local community and the broader ecological system.

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